

1 **Mixotrophic production of polyunsaturated fatty acids and carotenoids by the microalga**
2 ***Nannochloropsis gaditana***

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Abstract

Microalgae are potential sources of high-value lipids and colorants for use in foods, cosmetics and other applications. Biomass and metabolite productivities of photoautotrophic algae cultures are low because of limited availability of light. Therefore, mixotrophic cultures were investigated in parallel with photoautotrophic controls. In mixotrophy some of the energy and carbon are supplied in the form of dissolved organic substrates in addition to inorganic carbon and light being available. The aim was to compare productivities of biomass, fatty acids and carotenoid pigments in outdoor and indoor mixotrophic and photoautotrophic batch and continuous cultures. The edible and safe marine microalga *Nannochloropsis gaditana* was used in these studies. The alga could be grown mixotrophically using glucose and glycerol, but not acetate. Optimal concentrations of the organic carbon sources were 5 g L⁻¹ for glucose and 1 g L⁻¹ for glycerol. Mixotrophy substantially increased the biomass concentration and productivity relative to photoautotrophy. The maximum biomass productivity in mixotrophic batch cultures using glucose or glycerol was identical at 170 mg L⁻¹ d⁻¹, being 30% greater than control cultures. In continuous outdoor culture with glucose (5 g L⁻¹) mixotrophy at 12 °C, the total carotenoids in the biomass were 83% higher compared to photoautotrophic control biomass and the eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) productivity was 2.2-fold higher relative to controls. The maximum EPA productivity was 11 mg L⁻¹ d⁻¹. Glucose mixotrophy increased the total lipids content in the biomass by 34% relative to photoautotrophic operation.

Keywords: Eustigmatophyceae, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, mixotrophic growth, polyunsaturated fatty acids, carotenoids, eicosapentaenoic acid

43 **Introduction**

44 The marine green microalga *Nannochloropsis gaditana* has been extensively studied for lipid
45 production in photoautotrophic cultures (Ren et al. 2013; San Pedro et al. 2014; Camacho-
46 Rodríguez et al. 2014; 2015a; 2015b; Hallenbeck et al. 2015; Pedersen et al. 2018; Sung et al.
47 2018) both in closed outdoor photobioreactors (Camacho-Rodríguez et al. 2014; San Pedro et
48 al. 2014; 2016; Ledda et al. 2015; Riveros et al. 2018; Moraes et al. 2019) and in open raceway
49 ponds (Ledda et al. 2015; San Pedro et al. 2015; López et al. 2019). Inorganic nutrients from
50 wastewater have been used to produce the alga outdoors (Ledda et al. 2015).

51 In photoautotrophic cultures not limited by the supply of inorganic carbon, *N. gaditana*
52 can accumulate more than 48% of its dry mass as lipids in nitrogen limiting conditions
53 (Pedersen et al. 2018). This enhanced lipid accumulation under nitrogen limitation (Simionato
54 et al. 2013; Pedersen et al. 2018) is consistent with the predictions of the photoautotrophic
55 metabolic models of the alga (Shah et al. 2017). The main fatty acids accumulated comprise of
56 C16:0 (palmitic acid) and C16:1 (palmitoleic acid) (Pedersen et al. 2018). In addition, *N.*
57 *gaditana* is a good photoautotrophic producer of eicosapentaenoic acid (C20:5n3, EPA)
58 (Camacho-Rodríguez et al. 2014; Janssen et al. 2019), a high-value fatty acid with numerous
59 health benefits (Dyall 2015). *Nannochloropsis gaditana* also produces carotenoids such as
60 violaxanthin and vaucheraxanthin (Simionato et al. 2013). Both light intensity and temperature
61 have been shown to affect production of some carotenoid pigments in *N. gaditana* during
62 photoautotrophy (Lubián and Montero 1998). Other applications of the photoautotrophically
63 grown *N. gaditana* include its use as a well-established aquaculture feed (Ferreira et al. 2009;
64 Riveros et al. 2018). As an emerging application, extracts of *N. gaditana* may be useful in
65 cosmetics in view of their skin protection activity against induced oxidative stress (Letsiou et
66 al. 2017). The genome of the alga has been fully sequenced (Schwartz et al. 2018).

67 Photoautotrophic growth relies exclusively on inorganic carbon (e.g. bicarbonate, CO₂)
68 with the energy being obtained from light (Chojnacka and Marquez-Rocha 2004). Many
69 microalgae are capable of internalizing and metabolizing an organic carbon source (Neilson
70 and Lewin 1974; Day et al. 1991; Chojnacka and Marquez-Rocha 2004; Fang et al. 2004; Das
71 et al. 2011; Perez-Garcia et al. 2011; Cheirsilp and Torpee 2012; Sforza et al. 2012; Cerón-
72 García et al. 2013; Shene et al. 2016a; Bouyam et al. 2017). Such algae may be grown
73 heterotrophically in the dark using the relevant organic carbon source for energy and carbon
74 (Chojnacka and Marquez-Rocha 2004). Heterotrophic growth requires oxygen (Bouyam et al.
75 2017). In contrast to the above two modes of growth, mixotrophic growth uses both inorganic
76 and organic carbon and light. Photosynthesis occurs together with uptake and catabolism of the
77 organic carbon source (Chojnacka and Marquez-Rocha 2004; Perez-Garcia et al. 2011).
78 Mixotrophic growth may or may not require oxygen, as oxygen released through photosynthesis
79 may be sufficient for mixotrophy although the rate of consumption of the organic carbon source
80 may be limited in the absence of an external supply of oxygen. A dense culture of a microalga
81 growing photoautotrophically has a limited productivity as a significant volume of the culture
82 is always in the dark (Chisti 2013a; 2013b). No photosynthesis occurs in the dark and cells
83 consume stored organic carbon through respiration (Chisti 2013a). Productivity of mixotrophic
84 cultures can be as high as the productivity of a heterotrophic dark culture, but rapid periodic
85 exposure of the cells to light in a turbulent culture ensures that metabolites associated with
86 photosynthesis (e.g. many pigments) continue to be produced. Cells subjected to dark
87 heterotrophic growth may lack some of the metabolites they would produce under light.

88 Although many microalgae have been grown heterotrophically and mixotrophically
89 (Neilson and Lewin 1974; Day et al. 1991; Fang et al. 2004; Cerón-García et al. 2006; 2013;
90 Das et al. 2011; Perez-Garcia et al. 2011; Cheirsilp and Torpee 2012; Sforza et al. 2012;
91 Bouyam et al. 2017), no specific information appears to exist on mixotrophic production of *N*.

92 *gaditana*. How the production of EPA and carotenoids may be impacted by mixotrophy is
93 unknown. In a few cases, unidentified strains of *Nannochloropsis* have been shown to grow
94 mixotrophically on glucose (Fang et al. 2004; Cheirsilp and Torpee 2012) and ethanol (Fang et
95 al. 2004). The present work is focused on mixotrophic culture of *N. gaditana* to evaluate
96 production of lipids, EPA and carotenoids in batch and continuous-culture operations in
97 comparison with photoautotrophic controls.

98

99 **Materials and methods**

100 **Microorganism and indoor cultures**

101 *Nannochloropsis gaditana* strain B-3 was obtained from the Marine Culture Collection of the
102 Institute of Marine Sciences of Andalucía (CSIC, Cádiz, Spain). Stock cultures were maintained
103 photoautotrophically in 1 L Erlenmeyer flasks containing 700 mL of culture. The inoculum was
104 grown aseptically at 23 °C, under a constant incident irradiance of 100 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.
105 The flasks were continuously bubbled with air at 350 mL min^{-1} . No carbon dioxide was added.
106 The culture medium comprised of filter sterilized Mediterranean Sea water formulated with the
107 following agricultural grade inorganic components (g L^{-1}): KNO_3 1.0, $\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ 2.0×10^{-2} ,
108 $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{FeO}_7 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ 15×10^{-3} , $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 5.0×10^{-4} , $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 4.0×10^{-4} , ZnCl_2 8.0×10^{-4} ,
109 $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 9.0×10^{-4} , $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 8.0×10^{-5} , EDTA 0.015, thiamine 16.0×10^{-4} , biotin
110 6.0×10^{-5} , and cyanocobalamin 2.0×10^{-5} . This medium had been earlier established to be
111 optimal for photoautotrophic production of the algal biomass (Camacho-Rodríguez et al.
112 2015a).

113 For indoor cultures, the alga was grown in 500 mL Erlenmeyer flasks containing 250
114 mL of the culture medium. The above specified medium was sterilized (126 °C, 20 min) and
115 cooled. Separately filter sterilized (0.2 μm pore size membrane filter) organic carbon sources
116 (sodium acetate, MIXACE; glucose, MIXGLU; glycerol, MIXGLYC) were added to the

117 required concentration in mixotrophic operations. Only a single organic carbon substrate was
118 used in a given culture. The sterile medium was inoculated with cells in the linear growth phase.
119 A sufficient quantity of inoculum was added to obtain an initial dry biomass concentration of
120 0.2 g L^{-1} . Shake flasks were agitated at 150 rpm on an orbital shaker (Infors AG, Switzerland).
121 The flasks were continuously illuminated at $190 \text{ } \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Philips TLD 36W/54
122 fluorescent lamp) measured at the surface of the flasks. (The light level used for growing the
123 alga was of course higher than the level reported in an earlier paragraph for culture maintenance,
124 as growth is not sought during maintenance.) The initial pH was set at 8.0 and the incubation
125 temperature was $23 \pm 0.5 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$. In batch cultures, the initial concentration of the organic carbon
126 substrates varied between 1 and 15 g L^{-1} . Photoautotrophic control cultures (PHOTO; no
127 organic carbon source) were run in parallel with each mixotrophic culture.

128 All cultures were grown in triplicate. Triplicate samples were taken from each of the
129 culture vessels, when required. Data are average values \pm standard deviation of nine
130 experimental measurements at any instance.

131

132 **Outdoor cultures**

133 *Nannochloropsis gaditana* was grown in six identical outdoor flat-panel photobioreactors. Each
134 reactor consisted of a disposable polyethylene bag held within a steel cage, as previously
135 described (San Pedro et al. 2016). The larger flat face of each reactor was 1.7 m tall and 2.5 m
136 wide. The distance between the larger parallel flat faces was 0.09 m. The reactors were located
137 in Almería, Spain ($36^\circ 46' 00'' \text{ N}$, $2^\circ 30' 00'' \text{ W}$).

138 The reactors were aerated using a sparger located at the bottom. The air flow rate was
139 0.09 vvm (FR4L72BVBN flow meters, Key Instruments, USA). The pH was controlled by
140 injecting pure CO_2 whenever the pH rose above the set point value ($\text{pH} = 8$) and until the set
141 point was regained. The injection rate was 0.008 vvm . A combined temperature-pH probe (5342

142 pH electrode, Crison Instruments S.A., Spain) was located near the top of the reactor. A
143 thermoelectric pyranometer connected to an AC-420 adapter (LP-02, Geónica S.A., Spain) was
144 used to monitor the photosynthetically active incident solar radiation at the location of the
145 reactors (San Pedro et al. 2016). The cultures were continuously fed with fresh medium during
146 daylight hours at a dilution rate of 0.2 d^{-1} . The feeding ceased each night.

147 The experiments were conducted over a period of one year. The temperature was
148 monitored, but not controlled. The data were grouped based on the average daily temperature
149 in the autumn and winter growing seasons. The average culture temperature in autumn was 21
150 °C and in winter it was 12 °C. The mean values of the average incident irradiance in autumn
151 and winter were 580 and 421 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively. A steady state was taken to
152 exist if 4 consecutive daily measurements of the biomass concentration were within $\pm 5\%$ of the
153 averaged value. In all experiments, the culture samples were collected at steady state. The
154 biomass was recovered by centrifugation at $9000 \times g$ for 5 min. The biomass was washed with
155 0.5 M aqueous ammonium bicarbonate solution (Camacho-Rodríguez et al. 2013) and freeze-
156 dried (Telstar Cryodos 50, Telstar, Spain) for biochemical analyses.

157 Six replicate bioreactors were run in parallel. Once a steady state had been attained
158 based on the criterion specified earlier in this section, three replicate samples were taken during
159 the last three days of each steady state, from each bioreactor. The data shown are average values
160 \pm standard deviation of 54 measurements.

161

162 **Analytical procedures**

163 The biomass concentration was estimated by measuring the spectrophotometric absorbance at
164 540 nm of a suitably diluted culture sample and periodic corroboration with dry-weight
165 determinations (Camacho-Rodríguez et al. 2013). Occasionally, unidentified invasive species
166 appeared at low levels inside the reactors and, therefore, weekly microscopic (Nikon Eclipse

167 E200, Nikon Europe, The Netherlands) observations were made to ensure that *N. gaditana*
168 always represented more than 95% of the cells. If excessive contamination was detected, the
169 plastic bag was replaced and the culture was started afresh. The physiological health of the algal
170 cells was routinely checked by chlorophyll fluorescence measurements (AquaPen-C, AP-C 100
171 fluorimeter, Photon Systems Instruments, Czech Republic) to ensure that the ratio of variable
172 fluorescence (F_v) to maximum fluorescence (F_m) was >0.8 for unstressed cells. The cells were
173 dark adapted for 30 min prior to the measurements. Inorganic nitrate and phosphate were
174 measured to ensure a sufficiency of these key nutrients.

175 The fatty acids in freeze-dried biomass samples were transesterified in situ in
176 accordance with a published protocol (Rodríguez-Ruiz et al. 1998) and quantified by gas
177 chromatography (Agilent Technologies 6890 N Series Gas Chromatograph, USA). The
178 carotenoids were determined using a high-performance liquid chromatograph (Shimadzu
179 SPDM10AV, Shimadzu Corp, Japan) equipped with a photodiode array detector, as previously
180 explained (Cerón-García et al. 2018).

181 Analyses were performed on triplicate sample taken over the last three days of a steady
182 state operation. Therefore, the results represent average values \pm standard deviation of at least
183 nine replicate measurements.

184

185 **Results and discussion**

186 **Indoor culture**

187 Indoor batch cultures are useful for comparing the photoautotrophic and mixotrophic
188 production because they can be better controlled relative to the naturally illuminated outdoor
189 cultures. The mixotrophic biomass growth profiles of the alga on different substrates and
190 different initial concentrations of the substrates are shown in Fig. 1 in comparison with
191 photoautotrophic control cultures.

192 As shown in Fig. 1, in comparison with photoautotrophic controls, the biomass growth
193 was nearly as rapid and a higher final concentration of biomass was obtained during mixotrophy
194 on glucose (Fig. 1A) and glycerol (Fig. 1B). Thus, the alga effectively took up and metabolized
195 both glucose and glycerol. This was not the case when acetate was used (Fig. 1C). Compared
196 with acetate-containing media, the photoautotrophic control culture always outperformed in
197 terms of biomass growth (Fig. 1C). Although acetate is known to be readily metabolized by
198 many microalgae (Chapman et al. 2015; Smith et al. 2015), this was not so with *N. gaditana*.

199 The main biomass growth and productivity indices calculated using the data in Fig. 1
200 are summarized in Table 1. The table reveals that compared with photoautotrophic control
201 culture (PHOTO), the final biomass concentration in glucose and glycerol fed cultures (i.e.
202 MIXGLU5–15, MIXGLYC1–2) was at least as high, or higher, with MIXGLYC3 being an
203 exception. For glucose and glycerol, an increasing concentration of the carbon substrate in the
204 range examined, tended to reduce the final biomass concentration. Thus, mixotrophy on glucose
205 and glycerol was beneficial relative to control so long as the concentration of the organic carbon
206 source was kept low. High concentrations of sugars (glucose) and sugar alcohols (glycerol) are
207 known to suppress growth by reducing the water activity in a culture medium (Bouyam et al.
208 2017). In the media containing glucose at 5 g L⁻¹ and glycerol at 1–3 g L⁻¹, the maximum
209 specific growth rate was as high, or higher, than in the photoautotrophic control culture (Table
210 1). Thus, the ratio (μ_D) of the mixotrophic maximum specific growth rate to the
211 photoautotrophic maximum specific growth rate exceeded 1 (Table 1).

212 In the concentration range of 1–3 g L⁻¹, glycerol was a superior organic carbon source
213 compared with glucose at its best case concentration of 5 g L⁻¹. The carbon utilization efficiency
214 of the alga was much higher with glycerol compared to glucose. This was because each mole
215 of glucose provided 6 moles of organic carbon, but each mole of glycerol contained only 3
216 moles of carbon. Thus, at 1 g L⁻¹, glycerol provided an organic carbon molar amount that was

217 only 19.6% compared to the carbon provided by glucose at a concentration of 5 g L⁻¹, but in
218 terms of biomass production capabilities MIXGLYC1 was better than MIXGLU5 (Table 1).

219 No prior work appears to have been done on mixotrophic culture of *N. gaditana* per se.
220 A few mixotrophic studies have been reported for unspecified *Nannochloropsis* strains (Fang
221 et al. 2004; Cheirsilp and Torpee 2012). Using 30 mM glucose in 250 mL batch shake flask
222 cultures, Fang et al. (2004) attained a dry biomass concentration of 550 mg L⁻¹ in 8 days. This
223 is equivalent to a biomass productivity of 0.07 mg L⁻¹ d⁻¹, barely 41% of the productivity shown
224 in Table 1 for MIXGLU5 which had a glucose concentration (= 27.7 mM) quite close to that
225 used by Fang et al. (2004).

226

227 **Outdoor culture**

228 Although artificially illuminated indoor culture is suitable for small scale applications, it is
229 generally too expensive for large volume production of low-cost algal biomass.
230 Notwithstanding the good control of the culture environment that is possible indoors, outdoor
231 culture relying on freely available sunlight for illumination are essential for developing a
232 practicable production process. Thus, outdoor cultures were examined as discussed in this
233 section. In view of the results of the previous section, sodium acetate was eliminated from
234 outdoor studies as being a poor carbon substrate (Fig. 1C). In addition, only the media with
235 glucose at a concentration of 5 g L⁻¹ (i.e. MIXGLU5) and glycerol at a concentration of 1 g L⁻¹
236 (i.e. MIXGLYC1) were evaluated outdoors because they had provided the highest biomass
237 productivities indoors (Table 1).

238 In addition to biomass, the focus of outdoor studies was on production of total lipids
239 including the high value fatty acid EPA. In large outdoor cultures, control of temperature is
240 often impractical. Experiments were carried out in two different seasons with average daily
241 uncontrolled culture temperatures of 12 °C (winter) and 21 °C (autumn). The culture media

242 were MIXGLU5 and MIXGLYC1 with exactly the same other inorganic nutrients (Camacho-
243 Rodríguez et al. 2015a) as used in the above noted indoor cultures. All outdoor operations were
244 run as pseudo steady state continuous cultures. The key pseudo steady state parameters of the
245 outdoor cultures in the two media and at two temperatures are shown in Table 2. The relevant
246 data for the photoautotrophic control cultures are also shown (PHOTO, Table 2). For the two
247 photoautotrophic control cultures, the biomass productivity values in Table 2 at both the
248 temperatures were identical to those obtained independently by San Pedro et al. (2016) in
249 exactly the same conditions, including the flat-panel photobioreactor culture system, the
250 seasons, and the geographic location. This lent credibility to the reported data (Table 2) and its
251 reproducibility, for a reliable comparison with the mixotrophic data. In PHOTO control
252 cultures, the higher autumn mean temperature enhanced all production indices compared to the
253 winter season (Table 2), as is typical for algal cultures.

254 Comparing the two MIXGLYC1 cultures to the two PHOTO controls at identical
255 temperatures, the steady state biomass concentrations, the biomass productivities, and the lipid
256 productivities were essentially unaffected by mixotrophy on glycerol (Table 2), but the
257 mixotrophic cultures had distinctly higher EPA productivities (Table 2). In mixotrophic
258 glycerol cultures, the productivities were positively correlated with the culture temperature
259 (Table 2). A lack of impact of glycerol mixotrophy on biomass productivity in outdoor
260 operations is in dramatic contrast to the observations discussed earlier for indoor cultures. The
261 explanation for the difference is as follows: carbon dioxide was injected periodically in outdoor
262 cultures, but was not used indoors. Carbon dioxide is taken up by microalgae in the form of
263 bicarbonate (Shene et al. 2016b) and uptake of bicarbonate apparently interferes with and
264 suppresses the uptake of glycerol. Hence, there is barely any uptake of glycerol if carbon
265 dioxide is injected. This mutual antagonism between bicarbonate uptake and glycerol uptake

266 has been reported earlier with several other microalgae (Sforza et al. 2012; Cerón-García et al.
267 2013).

268 The glucose fed mixotrophic cultures (MIXGLU5, Table 2) performed substantially
269 better than the corresponding control (PHOTO, Table 2) cultures and the glycerol fed cultures
270 (MIXGLYC1, Table 2). For example, at 21 °C: the steady state biomass concentration was 77%
271 higher in MIXGLU5 relative to PHOTO (Table 2); the biomass productivity was 73% higher;
272 the EPA productivity was 29% higher; and the lipid productivity was 26% higher.

273 In the present work, no attempt was made to use nutrient starvation to promote lipid
274 accumulation in the biomass, although nitrogen starvation after growth has been shown to
275 greatly enhance the lipid content of the biomass in many algae including photoautotrophically
276 grown *N. gaditana* (Pedersen et al. 2018). Enhancement of lipid content of the biomass through
277 limiting non-carbon inorganic nutrients such as nitrogen and phosphorous, has been
278 demonstrated also in mixotrophic and heterotrophic cultures of some other microalgae
279 (Bouyam et al. 2017) and has the potential to be used with *N. gaditana*.

280 The productivity of EPA was highest in the two glucose fed mixotrophic cultures
281 (MIXGLU5, Table 2). In MIXGLU5 medium, the higher EPA productivity occurred at the
282 lower temperature, but this situation was reversed in the control cultures (PHOTO, Table 2).
283 Temperature has been found to both positively and negatively influence EPA production
284 depending on the alga. Further studies of how temperature might influence EPA and lipid
285 production in *N. gaditana* may be useful, but manipulating temperature in large scale outdoor
286 culture is often prohibitively expensive.

287 Barely any published data exist for EPA productivity in mixotrophic growth of *N.*
288 *gaditana*. For an unspecified *Nannochloropsis* strain grown mixotrophically on 30 mM glucose
289 and the same concentration of ethanol in 8-day indoor batch cultures, Fang et al. (2004) reported
290 a final EPA concentration of around 23 mg L⁻¹ for both substrates. In an equivalent

291 photoautotrophic batch culture, the final EPA concentration ($= 21.9 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) was nearly the
292 same as in the mixotrophic cultures. Using the above referenced EPA concentration and the 8-
293 day culture period (Fang et al. 2004), the EPA productivity of the mixotrophic cultures can be
294 shown to be $2.9 \text{ mg L}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$. This is far lower than the values shown in Table 2. For example,
295 the best case productivity with MIXGLU5 in Table 2 is 3.8-fold higher than observed by Fang
296 et al. (2004) in a medium with a glucose concentration quite close to the MIXGLU5.

297 Mixotrophic production of EPA using glycerol has been reported in the related alga
298 *Nannochloropsis oculata* (Shene et al. 2016a). The highest EPA concentration in a 10-day
299 indoor batch culture was $27.5 \pm 1.6 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, corresponding to a productivity of around 2.8 mg
300 $\text{L}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$ in a glycerol containing mixotrophic operation (Shene et al. 2016a). This productivity
301 was consistent with the values reported by Fang et al. (2004) in mixotrophic cultures on glucose
302 and ethanol, but quite low compared to the data in Table 2.

303

304 **Fatty acids and carotenoids**

305 The fatty acids and carotenoid pigments are important potential products of microalgae culture.
306 Therefore, these products were measured in the final biomass of the indoor batch cultures and
307 the biomass harvested during steady state operations of continuous outdoor cultures at a dilution
308 rate of 0.2 d^{-1} .

309 The fatty acid and carotenoid profiles of the biomass harvested from indoor batch
310 operations are shown in Fig. 2. Data are shown for the photoautotrophic control cultures
311 (PHOTO, Fig. 2) and the mixotrophic cultures MIXGLU5 and MIXGLYC1. The total fatty
312 acid content of the biomass was around 11% (w/w) irrespective of whether photoautotrophic or
313 mixotrophic operation was used (Fig. 2A). Thus, mixotrophy did not affect the total fatty acid
314 content relative to control. These results are consistent with the data reported for an unspecified
315 *Nannochloropsis* sp. where the total lipid content of the biomass was barely influenced by

316 whether the alga was grown photoautotrophically or mixotrophically (Fang et al. 2004). The
317 fatty acid composition of the lipids was not affected irrespective of whether the operation was
318 mixotrophic or photoautotrophic (Fig. 2A). The three major fatty acids in the lipids were
319 palmitic acid (C16:0), palmitoleic acid (C16:1) and EPA (C20:5n3) (Fig. 2A). The EPA content
320 was nearly 30% of the total fatty acids.

321 The total levels of the various carotenoids in the biomass produced in indoor operations
322 were similar irrespective of the culture mode (Fig. 2B). In heterotrophic cultures of some algae
323 in the dark, synthesis of some light-induced pigments may be low, or absent, compared to
324 biomass grown photoautotrophically (Li et al. 2015). In mixotrophic cultures, the light regime
325 is the same as in the corresponding photoautotrophic control culture, and therefore the results
326 in Fig. 2B are consistent with expectations.

327 The biomass produced in outdoor continuous cultures had all the same fatty acids (Fig.
328 3A) as the biomass grown in indoor batch operations (Fig. 2A), but also had measureable levels
329 of α -linolenic acid (C18:3n3). These differences may have been due to several possible factors
330 including differences in the light regimen (constant indoor illumination at 190 $\mu\text{mol photons}$
331 $\text{m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ versus cyclic natural illumination at 421 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ for the data in Fig. 3),
332 the prevailing temperature (23 ± 0.5 °C indoors versus 12 °C for the data in Fig. 3), and the
333 supply of inorganic carbon (supplied outdoors versus not supplied indoors). EPA (C20:5n3)
334 was generally the predominant fatty acid, especially in the biomass produced in outdoor cultures
335 (Fig. 3A). For both indoor batch and outdoor continuous cultures, whether the operation was
336 photoautotrophic (PHOTO) or mixotrophic (MIXGLU5, MIXCLYC1) had relatively minor
337 effect on the fatty acid composition of the lipids (Fig. 2A, Fig. 3A).

338 In the biomass produced outdoors, the average total fatty acid content (TFA, Fig. 3B)
339 irrespective of the culture mode (PHOTO, MIXGLYC1, MIXGLU5) was 11.9%, or essentially
340 the same as in the biomass produced indoors (Fig. 2A). The polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA,

341 Fig. 3B) were the predominant class of fatty acids. The proportions of monounsaturated fatty
342 acids (MUFA) and saturated fatty acids (SFA) in total fatty acids (TFA) were roughly equal
343 (Fig. 3B).

344 The total lipid (TL) content of the biomass produced mixotrophically (i.e. MIXGLU5,
345 MIXGLYC1 in Fig. 3B) were significantly greater relative to the control biomass (PHOTO,
346 Fig. 3B). The average total lipid content of the biomass grown in the three modes (i.e. PHOTO,
347 MIXGLU5, MIXGLYC1; Fig. 3B) was 24% (w/w) and the best case value for the mixotrophic
348 culture MIXGLU5 (Fig. 3B) was 27.1%. Both these were low compared to earlier reports for
349 mixotrophically grown biomass of other *Nannochloropsis* algae (Fang et al. 2004; Shene et al.
350 2016a).

351 The total lipid level was low because the biomass was not starved of any nutrient. Lipid
352 accumulation in microalgae generally occurs when nutrient supply limits growth. In carbon-
353 sufficient but nitrogen limited photoautotrophic cultures, *N. gaditana* has been shown to
354 accumulate more than 48% of its dry mass as lipids (Pedersen et al. 2018). Similarly, the total
355 lipid content of the dry biomass reported by Fang et al. (2004) were $38.7 \pm 2.1\%$ (w/w) in
356 biomass produced mixotrophically on glucose (Fang et al. 2004) and $34.6 \pm 0.6\%$ in the biomass
357 grown mixotrophically on ethanol. The total lipid content reported by Fang et al. (2004) for
358 glucose mixotrophy was around 28% higher than our highest value for MIXGLU5 (Fig. 3B).
359 The explanation lay in nitrogen starvation of the biomass towards the end of the batch culture
360 in the work of Fang et al. (2004), but absence of starvation in the present work. The lowest
361 measured nitrate concentration at steady state (dilution rate = 0.2 d^{-1}) was 248 mg L^{-1} ,
362 confirming an absence of nitrogen limitation.

363 The initial KNO_3 concentration used in our work was 1 g L^{-1} , corresponding to an initial
364 nitrate concentration of 613 mg L^{-1} . In contrast, Fang et al. (2004) used the standard f/2 medium
365 that has a nitrate concentration of only 54.7 mg L^{-1} . Data presented by Fang et al. (2004) do

366 show the nitrate concentrations declining to less than 15 mg L⁻¹ in the final 3 days of their
367 mixotrophic cultures. Similarly, a high lipid content (>30% by dry weight) was also reported
368 in the final biomass of the related alga *N. oculata* grown mixotrophically using glycerol in a
369 10-day batch culture (Shene et al. 2016a). The explanation once again lay in the f/2 medium
370 used (Shene et al. 2016a) compared to the high-nitrogen medium of the present work.

371 Based on the well-known principles of continuous culture (Bailey and Ollis 1986; Chisti
372 2010), in a steady-state operation with a stable concentration of the biomass, the dilution rate
373 must equal the specific growth rate. The dilution rate used in the outdoor continuous culture
374 studies was 0.2 d⁻¹. This value was higher than the highest value of the maximum specific
375 growth rate observed in any indoor batch operation (Table 1), but the indoor operations had a
376 much lower light level (= 190 μmol photons m⁻² s⁻¹) compared to the lowest outdoor light level
377 (= 421 μmol photons m⁻² s⁻¹ in autumn) and therefore a higher specific growth rate (= 0.2 d⁻¹)
378 could be stably maintained outdoors.

379 The carotenoids profiles of the outdoor grown biomass are shown in Fig. 4. All the listed
380 carotenoids were produced to a measureable level in all cultures irrespective of the mode of
381 growth, but mixotrophy substantially enhanced to total carotenoids in the biomass compared to
382 photoautotrophic control (Fig. 4). The total carotenoids in the biomass grown with glucose
383 mixotrophy were 1.8-fold more than in the control biomass (PHOTO, Fig. 4). Similarly, with
384 glycerol mixotrophy, the total carotenoids in the biomass were 1.5-fold greater relative to
385 control. This suggests MIXGLU5 to be best for carotenoids production.

386

387 **Concluding remarks**

388 Mixotrophic production of the biomass, lipids and carotenoids of the microalga *N. gaditana*
389 was shown to be possible using glucose or glycerol, but not acetate. The optimal concentrations
390 of the organic carbon sources were 5 g L⁻¹ for glucose and 1 g L⁻¹ for glycerol. In the absence

391 of any nutrient limitations in outdoor continuous cultures at a dilution rate of 0.2 d⁻¹ during
392 winter (12 °C average daily culture temperature), the total lipid productivity was 2.7-fold higher
393 relative to photoautotrophic control when glucose (5 g L⁻¹) mixotrophy was used. For the same
394 mixotrophic operation, the EPA productivity was 2.2-fold higher than controls. The total
395 carotenoids in the mixotrophically grown biomass was 83% higher compared to control.
396 Therefore, compared with photoautotrophy, mixotrophic operation on glucose is potentially
397 useful for enhancing production of lipids, EPA and carotenoids in *N. gaditana* cultures that are
398 not nutrient limited.

399

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406

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- 535

536 **Table 1** Indoor batch culture parameters

537

Culture type ^a	C_b (g L ⁻¹)	S_f (g L ⁻¹)	μ_{\max} (d ⁻¹)	P_{\max} (g L ⁻¹ d ⁻¹)	μ_D (-)	P_D (-)
PHOTO	0.92±0.01	-	0.14±0.00	0.13±0.00	-	-
MIXGLU5	1.08±0.07	1.42±0.03	0.16±0.00	0.17±0.01	1.08	1.26
MIXGLU10	0.92±0.07	3.45±0.04	0.14±0.00	0.13±0.01	0.96	0.95
MIXGLU15	0.97±0.05	4.65±0.05	0.14±0.01	0.13±0.01	0.96	1.01
MIXGLYC1	1.07±0.03	0.32±0.06	0.16±0.00	0.17±0.01	1.11	1.29
MIXGLYC2	0.98±0.05	0.59±0.08	0.15±0.02	0.15±0.02	1.03	1.09
MIXGLYC3	0.88±0.02	1.50±0.07	0.15±0.00	0.13±0.00	1.04	0.99
MIXACE5	0.57±0.01	ND	0.08±0.01	0.05±0.00	0.56	0.35
MIXACE10	0.64±0.13	ND	0.06±0.02	0.04±0.02	0.58	0.39
MIXACE15	0.44±0.05	ND	0.03±0.01	0.01±0.00	0.21	0.09

538

539 C_b , Final biomass concentration in the stationary phase; S_f , final substrate concentration in the stationary phase (ND, not determined because of the
540 low biomass productivity with this substrate); μ_{\max} , maximum specific growth rate; P_{\max} , maximum biomass productivity; μ_D , dimensionless
541 maximum specific growth rate (i.e. μ_{\max} divided by the maximum specific growth rate for photoautotrophic control); P_D , maximum biomass
542 productivity relative to photoautotrophic control in batch cultures.

543

544 ^a PHOTO, photoautotrophic culture; MIXGLU5, mixotrophic glucose (5 g L⁻¹); MIXGLU10, mixotrophic glucose (10 g L⁻¹); MIXGLU15,
545 mixotrophic glucose (15 g L⁻¹); MIXGLYC1, mixotrophic glycerol (1 g L⁻¹); MIXGLYC2, mixotrophic glycerol (2 g L⁻¹); MIXGLYC3,

546 mixotrophic glycerol (3 g L⁻¹); MIXACE5, mixotrophic acetate (5 g L⁻¹); MIXACE10, mixotrophic acetate (10 g L⁻¹); MIXACE15, mixotrophic
547 acetate (15 g L⁻¹).

548

549

550 **Table 2** Outdoor continuous culture parameters^a

551

Culture type ^b	Temperature (°C)	Biomass concentration (g L ⁻¹)	Biomass productivity (g L ⁻¹ d ⁻¹)	EPA productivity (mg L ⁻¹ d ⁻¹)	Total lipid productivity (mg L ⁻¹ d ⁻¹)
PHOTO	21	0.71±0.01	0.15±0.01	7.05±0.00	30.09±1.04
PHOTO	12	0.52±0.08	0.10±0.03	5.01±0.04	20.07±0.55
MIXGLU5	21	1.26±0.06	0.26±0.04	9.10±0.04	37.81±0.70
MIXGLU5	12	0.97±0.06	0.20±0.01	11.02±0.04	54.00±0.88
MIXGLYC1	21	0.73±0.06	0.15±0.02	7.85±0.03	29.00±0.12
MIXGLYC1	12	0.57±0.02	0.11±0.01	5.50±0.06	21.02±1.14

552

553 The values shown are average of the last three days in steady state cultivation.

554 ^a The dilution rate for all continuous cultures was 0.2 d⁻¹.555 ^b PHOTO, photoautotrophic culture; MIXGLU5, mixotrophic glucose (5 g L⁻¹); MIXGLYC1,
556 mixotrophic glycerol (1 g L⁻¹).

557

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560

562 **Fig. 1** Biomass production of *N. gaditana* in indoor batch cultures: comparison between
563 photoautotrophic (PHOTO) and mixotrophic growth using different organic carbon sources (g
564 L⁻¹): (A) 5.0, 10.0 and 15.0 of glucose (MIXGLU_n); (B) 1.0, 2.0 and 3.0 of glycerol
565 (MIXGLYC_n); and (C) 5.0, 10.0 and 15.0 of sodium acetate (MIXACE_n). Data shown are
566 average values and standard deviations of nine measurements (3 biological replicates ×
567 triplicate samples)
568

569

570 **Fig. 2** Types of fatty acids (A) and carotenoids (B) in *N. gaditana* final biomass grown in indoor
 571 batch cultures at 23 ± 0.5 °C. PHOTO: photoautotrophic control; MIXGLU5: mixotrophic
 572 culture on glucose (5 g L^{-1}); and MIXGLYC1: mixotrophic culture on glycerol (1 g L^{-1}). (Fatty

573 acids: Myristic acid, C14:0; palmitic acid, C16:0; palmitoleic acid, C16:1n7; oleic acid,
 574 C18:1n9; linoleic acid, C18:2n6; α -linolenic acid, C18:3n3; arachidonic acid, C20:4n6; and
 575 eicosapentaenoic acid, C20:5n3.) Data shown are average values and standard deviations of
 576 nine measurements (3 biological replicates \times triplicate samples)

577

578 **Fig. 3** Fatty acids profile (A) and classes of fatty acids (B) in *N. gaditana* biomass grown in
 579 outdoor continuous cultures at a dilution rate of 0.2 d⁻¹ at 12 °C. PHOTO: photoautotrophic
 580 control; MIXGLYC1: mixotrophic culture on glycerol (1 g L⁻¹); and MIXGLU5: mixotrophic
 581 culture on glucose (5 g L⁻¹). SFA, Saturated fatty acids; MUFA, monounsaturated fatty acids;
 582 PUFA, polyunsaturated fatty acids; TL, total lipids; TFA, total fatty acids. (Fatty acids: Myristic
 583 acid, C14:0; palmitic acid, C16:0; palmitoleic acid, C16:1n7; oleic acid, C18:1n9; linoleic acid,
 584 C18:2n6; α -linolenic acid, C18:3n3; arachidonic acid, C20:4n6; and eicosapentaenoic acid,
 585 C20:5n3.) Data shown are average values and standard deviations of 54 measurements (6
 586 biological replicates \times triplicate samples per day at steady state \times 3 days during steady state)

587
 588 **Fig. 4** Carotenoids profiles in the algal biomass grown in continuous cultures at a dilution rate
 589 of 0.2 d⁻¹ at 12 °C. PHOTO, photoautotrophic control; MIXGLYC1, mixotrophic with glycerol
 590 (1 g L⁻¹); MIXGLU5, mixotrophic with glucose (5 g L⁻¹). Data shown are average values and

591 standard deviations of 54 measurements (6 biological replicates × triplicate samples per day at
592 steady state × 3 days during steady state)
593